

UNIVERSITY OF NAMUR

POLICY TO ADDRESS GENDER-BASED VIOLENCE

NATIONAL CONTEXT

National context: Protection against violence and moral or sexual harassment at work is provided under a federal law that dates from 11 June 2002. This law is not specific to research or higher education settings, it protects all types of workers, including those working at universities and research organisations (administrative, technical, and research staff). This law provides a general framework, which is then implemented and, in some cases, further developed by some employers.

Regional context

In the French-Speaking Community (Wallonia-Brussels Federation), an inter-university committee dedicated to the promotion of gender equality in research was established by a decree (a federal level law) on 10 March 2016. It is called the Committee for Women in Science (*Comité Femmes & Sciences*) and the Academy of Research and Higher Education (ARES) serves as the Secretariat. Every university nominates a gender focal point representative, who participates in the work of the Committee for Women and Science and is responsible for publishing an annual report on the state of gender equality at the university, drafting a joint synthesis report, and increasing the visibility and sharing information about gender at the university and among the general public. After the Parliament of the French-Speaking Community passed a resolution to support higher education institutions in their fight against gender discrimination, a special Commission on Gender in Higher Education (CoGES) was created in December 2020. This Standing Commission acts as a space for crosscutting discussion on gender issues. One of the aims is to support institutions in their fight against harassment in higher education institutions and in training professionals to detect and support victims of violence.

INSTITUTIONAL POLICY

UNamur has been fighting against gender discrimination since 2011 with the creation of the Gender Group and then, in 2013, with the creation of a Vice-Rectorate responsible for developing this policy. In addition to the gender focal person mentioned above, UNamur has also instituted another position dedicated to designing and implementing policies on harassment and violence in the university.

The policy mix relating to GBV consists of non-dedicated policies, that is, general policies addressing GBV as a part of the policy. The fight against harassment is one of the four priorities that the university has adopted for the period 2020-2021. The implementation of an anti-harassment policy for staff and students includes:

- an unequivocal commitment by the university to combat all forms of sexual or moral harassment through preventive or, where appropriate, remedial action, including disciplinary sanctions;
- a clear identification of the places where victims can be received and protected in crisis situations;
- a clear identification of the 'harassment situation' entry point for anyone seeking help ('one-stop shop');
- a system for referring and accompanying people to obtain medical and psychological support or to an internal (disciplinary procedure) or external (police) complaint procedure, including the coordination of the various services involved;
- the development and implementation of procedures to fill existing gaps.

At the time of the mapping, it was planned to set up an entry point ('help desk') at the beginning of the 2021-22 academic year (September 21), following the adoption of the policy.

URLs

- › Policy Declaration on gender:
<https://www.unamur.be/genre/PolitiqueduGenreJanvier2020priorits.pdf>

Entry into force: 2020 for the gender brief and September 2021 for the help desk.

TRAINING

Training for the personnel in charge of the help desk.

ROLE IN KNOWLEDGE PRODUCTION

An interdisciplinary master's degree in gender studies has been created that draws on the combined expertise of the six universities in the Wallonia-Brussels Federation in this field by organising and jointly offering specialised and original courses. This master's degree offers multi- and interdisciplinary training in the field of gender studies grounded in an intersectional perspective, and GBV is one of the subjects it addresses.

CONTENT OF THE POLICY

Forms of gender-based violence: The gender brief refers to all type of harassment (including gender harassment) and sexual harassment.

- | | |
|---|--|
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Economic and Financial Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Physical Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Stalking |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Psychological Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Organisational Violence |
| <input type="checkbox"/> Sexual Violence | <input type="checkbox"/> Online Violence |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Sexual Harassment | <input type="checkbox"/> Other |
| <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Gender-Based Harassment | |

7Ps covered: The policy addresses the following **6Ps**: prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, provision of services, and partnership.

UniSAFE has developed the 7P model as a basis for analysing policies on GBV. For more information, see the deliverable report D3.1 Report on the conceptual and theoretical state of the art: <https://unisafe-gbv.eu/project-public-deliverables/>

The P for policy is considered in place if the institution has a GBV-focused policy or more general policies that have a procedure for reporting and investigating.

Intersectionality addressed

No

Specific vulnerable groups

Not defined

Target groups

Policy Declaration on Gender

Help Desk

The gender brief is aimed at academic and non-academic staff.

Bystanders addressed: No.

The new help desk only targets students.

Role of perpetrators addressed: No.

IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POLICY

Indicators: No.

Monitoring: Yes. A monitoring process has been set up to monitor the profiles of victims and the circumstances of incidents and to identify risk factors.

Evaluation: Yes. The implementation policy is evaluated and addressed in the annual gender report.

INSTITUTIONAL PROCEDURE

None. Complaints can only be filed through an online form (anonymous or not) to be able to monitor the profile of victims, circumstances and identify risk factors.

This document reflects the situation as of January 2022.

Acknowledgment: *this vignette has been created on the basis of the work carried out by national researcher Nathalie Wuiame in 2021, as part of the deliverable report D5.1 Inventory of policies and measures to respond to GBV in European universities and research organisations (2022). Available here: https://zenodo.org/record/5939082#.YfvXE_jTW5c*

